

The Pulsation Properties of λ Bootis Stars I — The Southern TESS Sample (Murphy et al. 2020) Appendix B.

In this online-only appendix we show Fourier transforms of the TESS light curves. For all targets, a panel from 0 to 80 c/d shown. For stars with only FFI data, integer multiples of the Nyquist frequency are shown with vertical dashed red lines. For δ Sct stars, a zoomed plot focussing around the area of the strongest p mode is also shown adjacent to the first panel, using that same amplitude range (y-axis limit) for consistency. The extracted frequencies given in Table 1 of the main text are indicated with red diamonds, where possible. Note that peaks corresponding to the harmonics of g modes are not identified as p modes in any case.

Figure B1. Fourier transforms of λ Boo star light curves.

Figure B2. Fourier transforms of λ Boo star light curves.

Figure B3. Fourier transforms of λ Boo star light curves.

Figure B4. Fourier transforms of λ Boo star light curves.

Figure B5. Fourier transforms of λ Boo star light curves.

Figure B6. Fourier transforms of λ Boo star light curves.

Figure B7. Fourier transforms of λ Boo star light curves.

Figure B8. Fourier transforms of λ Boo star light curves.

Figure B9. Fourier transforms of λ Boo star light curves.

Figure B10. Fourier transforms of λ Boo star light curves.

Figure B11. Fourier transforms of λ Boo star light curves.

Figure B12. Fourier transforms of λ Boo star light curves.

Figure B13. Fourier transforms of λ Boo star light curves.

Figure B14. Fourier transforms of λ Boo star light curves.